

“Co-design is an inclusive approach for fashion designers working with traditional crafts”: Exploring ethics of craft collaborations in design education

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Abstract: Despite being a key contributor to the Indian fashion design industry, traditional artisans are often exploited in the name of help. Designers have been exploiting both the aesthetic style and skills of the traditional artisan communities. In absence of equal opportunities, trends indicate many artisans are leaving their practice. This paper suggests co-design as a way forward for designers to collaborate with traditional artisans. Co-design is proposed over the top-down approach of design intervention where a designer or design students provides design for artisan to follow. It is advocated to introduce co-design as a component in design education as more ethical pedagogy. The essays present two case studies of collaboration between design students and traditional artisans as a methodology. The findings suggest co-design as a creatively, more enriching approach for both designers and artisans when collaborating.

Practical Implications: The essay concludes with implications for designers and design students to consider for an ethically sustainable collaboration. The co-design approach allows the artisan agency to innovate within their heritage craft, thus addressing the problem of appropriation and exploitation.

Keywords: Appropriation; Co-design; Craftspeople; Ethics; Fashion; Traditional Artisan

1. Introduction

Traditional artisans have been a major contributor in the growth of the fashion industry in India. Most well-known fashion designers achieved success relying on the skills of craftspeople and manipulating the aesthetics of traditional crafts. To name a few, Raw Mango draws on Varanasi brocades and Chanderi weaving, Abu Jain Sandeep Khosla on Chikankari embroidery, Sabyasachi Mukherjee on Zardozi embroidery and Varanasi brocades weaving, Anit Aroa on Jamdhani weaving and so on. Despite being a key contributor to the designer labels success, traditional craftspeople largely remain anonymous and often exploited. Fashion movements such as “Who made my clothes” and “Fair trade” have brought awareness to the ethics of textile and clothing workers (Shaw et al. 2007). However, the scope of these movements does not address issues specific to traditional Indian craft communities. In recent years, for the first time India-Fashion-Week included traditional craft people offering them space and credit (Kumar 2017). However, these are usually one-time instances; more action is required to sensitize the fashion design fertility and design education. Introducing equity and ethics, in practice as an approach within design education would address is making a positive impact in this discretion. The problem is threefold, exploitation of artisan aesthetics, i.e. appropriation without giving a creative voice to the artisan, not crediting the artisan and unfair wages. This paper focuses on the first two issues that would empower the artisan to have a voice to achieve a fair equity; in absence of which the artisans would stop practicing their heritage of crafts. According to trends the number of craft people is

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Cite as – Ghai L. (2022). “Co-design is an inclusive approach for fashion designers working with traditional crafts”: exploring ethics of craft collaboration in design education
International Journal of Design and Allied Sciences, 1 (1), 20-24.

drastically decreasing (Chatterjee 2016). This paper also illustrates what usually the idea of help means when offered to the craftspeople. The paper aims to propose ‘co-design’ as an ethical and emphatic approach for designers and design students interested in working with traditional Indian craftspeople. Two collaborative case studies between design students and traditional artisans as a methodology informs the findings of this essay.

2. Literature Review

Although the percentage of craftspeople is diminishing at a high rate, given India is the second largest population in the world, there are still plentiful craft people. According to Frater and Hawley (2018), “In the developing world, craftsmanship is still relatively plentiful. Unfortunately, that very fact has led to its exploitation and devaluation.” There is usually an economic and educational power difference between designers and craft people. When fashion designers collaborate with traditional artisans, they exploit the craft community’s aesthetics. Despite this, appropriation of crafts in India is still to become a larger debate (Ghai 2020). According to Frater, women's crafts in Kutch did not involve the aspect of production; each article embroidered was an expression of creativity, unique in itself. Styles are concepts belonging to communities, not just technique skill of making. (Marati 2012).

The primary question to consider is why to engage in co-designing over the popular format of top down design intervention; with fashion designers giving solutions to craftspeople? Sanders and Stappers (p10, 2008) in the context of: What is going on in design practice? States, “We are no longer simply designing products for users. We are designing for the future experiences of people, communities and cultures...” Hence, co-designing is proposed as a working methodology for professional designers who desire to engage with traditional artisan communities with the intent to contribute towards their growth. Murray (2010) illustrates the example of the brand ‘Polly and Me’; co-designing is employed as a meaningful approach. Two Australian sisters Cath and Ange Braid, founders of this brand, involved women artisans in Pakistan by giving them a platform to develop their own designs. Neil and Ravetz (Ravetz et al. 2013) in ‘Collaboration through Craft’ note that the value of collaboration depends on more than one understanding of creativity. The fashion designers have gained much thriving on artisan’s creativity, on the other hand artisan reduced to skills workers. Given the challenges many artisans remain hand to mouth. Often ‘help’ is offered to artisans, although this may seem a good proposition it only makes artisans dependent rather than independent. The next section unpacks ‘help’, as it is often offered.

3. What ‘help’ means?

Kutch, Gujarat is one of the richest regions of traditional textile crafts that attracts several visitors. These visitors usually identified themselves as entrepreneurs, designers or design students, with the prime propaganda of helping the craftsperson by providing craft people with new designs through intervention. The crafts are produced by a diversity of traditional communities practicing the crafts of hand weaving, Ajrakh printing, batik, Bandhani and exquisite embroideries. The women of the Rabari, Ahir, Mutva, Meghval, Jat, Patel, Bharavad and Rajput communities practice distinctive community styles of hand embroidery and traditionally had the knowledge of stitching clothes. Rabari and Ahir often combine katab with embroidery for articles of home decoration; whereas the craft of patchwork is popular among the elderly women of most of the communities for making domestic quilts with a chief objective of utilizing old fabrics. Traditionally, the women never engaged in stitching for commercial purposes. Over the past four decades, Kutch has experienced natural calamities in the form of droughts (Nathan 2001), two cyclones, and a major earthquake in 2001. In addition, the social and economic changes have forced women artisans in particular to make their crafts for commercial purpose, generally reducing them to the status of laborers. In view of this background the visitor comes into the picture. Usually with economic leverage and access to customers the visitor in reality looks for help, rather than helping. Against the challenges, where artisans had to create for a distant market; where there were too many visitors intending to help, a popular practice has been dictating work to traditional artisans, often referred as design intervention.

4. Teaching Open Electives at NID, Ahmedabad

Proposals were invited to conduct a course on ‘Design for Social innovation and sustainability’ at National Institute of Design (NID), in 2012 and on the theme ‘Drawing- by design’, in 2015. Conceptualizing and teaching both these courses helped me further understand the dynamics of relations between various stakeholders that include: design students, artisans, design institutes, administrators and teachers. Women artisans practicing the craft of *katab*, patchwork were invited to partner with design students. An exposure to the environment of the artisans, their economical housing conditions, personal background and style of working enabled the students to comprehend the context of the artisans in the current scenario. An exposure of how and from where the women acquired tailoring remnants, old clothes and surplus textiles enabled the students to have a fresh perspective for their own sourcing. In terms of designing, the collaboration was led by the NID students. However, besides assisting in stitching, the artisans contributed to creative decision-making, offering suggestions at various stages such as application of colour combinations, layout and finishing. As a tangible output of the elective, each student had a quilt co-designed and co-created by the artisans and the design students. The artisans assumed multiple roles, as collaborators in co-creating and co-designing, as assistants, as students as well as assistant-teachers. The students expressed that the course was a great learning experience.

All 14 students participating in the course felt that by collaborating with the artisans they had learnt something new which would contribute to their growth as designers. According to Kumbhar (2012), an automobile designer, “I experienced that working with hands has emotions (I made a completely handmade quilt). There are no emotions working with a machine as the machine follows an algorithm. The hand changes this. Working with artisan- we learnt skills and philosophy. I learnt how contrast in colours could be used to advantage. I can now apply soft materials in automobile design, the idea of personalized: handmade for luxury cars.” (Ghai 2015) According to another student Dhanapalan, “I enjoyed using new materials. I have never co-designed before; this helped me break out of my shell. The process of teaching was really good. Sourcing materials was a new experience. (Working with the artisans) I learnt how to sit in one place and work. I learnt patience and a new perspective to designing!” Design student, Chandrasekharan, sums up that “I learnt about co-working, patience, valuing artisans and their knowledge. I learnt how sustainability can be a concept to make valuable designs.” It may be concluded from the responses of the design students that co-designing with artisans brought new ways of design thinking, adding a fresh approach to their practice. All the artisans involved in the collaboration responded that compared to their previous experiences of work where they were dictated by the designer to follow instruction; they found the approach of being involved in creative decision making more valuable. According to the *katab* artisan Viashali Chauhan (2012), this was the most respectable collaboration she experienced in her life; where she felt recognized as an artist and not a mechanical job-worker. She stated, “Artisans do not work for only money, we want an equal voice in collaborations and recognition.” These statements also respond to the question raised earlier of why co-design.

Figure 1. Student and artisan engaged in co-design at NID, 2015 (Photo credit: Lokesh Ghai).

5. Teaching Finishing and Collection Development at KRV

In 2011, I taught the course ‘Finishing and Collection Development’ at Kala Raksha Vidhyalay. India’s premier design school to empower traditional artisans established by Judy Frater. The course had a component of co-design between NID students, artists enrolled to study design at KRV. The NID students found it a challenge to co-design, they had only experienced the pedagogy of getting their designs translated into handcrafted textile by artisans. The NID students expressed their disappointment in not having the opportunity to individually design. The students were keen on ‘helping’ the artisans by giving them designs.

One of the root causes for the lack of success in second collaboration is inclusivity and gap exposure to courses on co-design in India.

If the problem of not valuing traditional artisans for their creativity is not addressed at the schooling level of design education, it will only become exaggerated at the professional level; where the prime approach of professionals towards artisans would be to help them, by giving them design.

6. Conclusion and Practical implication

The finding of the collaborations indicated that co-design has value as a design process that results in enriching results; it adds fresh perspective to designing. Introducing co-design in design education would lay the foundation towards an inclusive approach for designs and artisans. The approach is more ethical and considerate for artisans who have usually been exploited in the name of help. The co-design approach also addresses the ethics of appropriation and exploitation of artisans by giving them agency to innovate within their heritage craft. The co-design approach would enable in building better relationships among professional designers and artisans. For the success of the collaboration it is important fashion designers not perceive artisans who just need help; as this approach immediately separates the artisan from a designer. By assuming that the artisan needs help, instead of making the artisan independent, one is making the artisan even more dependent. Acknowledge and engage in dialogue as a starting point: Rather than simply dictate a dialogue should be initiated to compliment the strengths of the artisan and designer. Designers should take a learning approach; learn what the artisans have to offer and what their traditions are, before thinking of how to work with the artisans. Designers should offer credit and fair remuneration that accounts for creativity, traditional knowledge and not just hand-skills.

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